

S1. Full scoring worksheet (Table 2 complete, blank template)

Purpose:

Blank scoring worksheet for criterion-level assessment (M0–M5 / IE / N/A) with evidence logging and note tags for blind spots [BS] and risks [R].

Dimension	Criterion	Assigned level (M0–M5 / N/A / IE)	Evidence (≥2 observable indicators)	Artifact/trace (≥1)	Notes (incl. blind spot hypothesis [BS], risk of drift [R])	N/A justification (if applicable)
D1	C1 Intention clarity					
	C2 Vision–frontline dialogue					
	C3 Long-term orientation					
D2	C4 Work practice mastery					
	C5 Process understanding					
	C6 Error management					
D3	C7 Knowledge transfer					
	C8 Collective learning					
	C9 Meaning at work (sense-making)					
D4	C10 Quality of human relations					
	C11 Cross-role cooperation					
	C12 Recognition of work and craftsmanship					
D5	C13 Accountability and steering					
	C14 Human–system interaction (N/A possible)					
	C15 System adaptability and resilience					